

THE RELEVANCE OF RESEARCH INTO INCLUSIVE AND ACCESSIBLE DESIGN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOFTWARE INTERFACES

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Abstracts. The article discusses the relevance of research on inclusive and accessible design in the context of software interface development. It analyses the social, ethical, technical, and economic aspects of digital product accessibility. Particular attention is paid to the role of accessibility standards (WCAG), the participation of users with disabilities in research and design processes, and the impact of inclusive design on software usability and competitiveness. The need for further interdisciplinary research in the field of accessibility as a key factor in the sustainable development of the digital environment is justified.

Keywords: inclusive design, accessible design, software interfaces, WCAG, user-centred design, digital accessibility.

The digitalisation of society is leading to an increase in the role of software interfaces in people's everyday lives. At the same time, unequal access to digital products remains a significant problem for a large proportion of users, including persons with disabilities, older persons and users with temporary limitations. In this context, research into inclusive and accessible design is particularly relevant, as it aims to overcome digital barriers and ensure equal opportunities for the use of software interfaces (Чемерис & Брянцева, 2021).

A classic example of the fallacy of focusing on the "norm" is the research conducted in the 1940s in the United States during the design of military aircraft cockpits. Analysis of anthropometric data from 4,063 pilots across ten parameters relevant to aircraft cockpit design (including height, upper limb length, and other indicators affecting the ergonomic characteristics of the workspace) showed that none of them corresponded to the model of the "average pilot." For each parameter, a central interval was determined, covering 30% of the values around the average (for

example, with an average height of 176 cm, the analysed range was 170–180 cm). Based on a combination of these intervals, a generalised model of the so-called "average pilot" was formed. A further comparison of the individual anthropometric data of all study participants with the resulting model showed that none of the pilots met all the specified parameters at the same time. Even after reducing the model to three parameters and re-analysing it, it was found that only 3.5% of pilots fell within the central 30% range for all three indicators. This study laid the foundation for recognizing the need to design flexible systems that allow for adjustment and adaptation rather than universal standardization.

An important aspect of the evolution of understanding accessibility is the visual representation of disability (Fig.1.). The traditional International Symbol of Accessibility (ISA), enshrined in ISO 7001, has historically associated disability primarily with limited mobility and the use of a wheelchair. This approach has contributed to a narrow view of disability and has not taken into account a wide range of visible and invisible impairments, including cognitive, sensory and neurodiverse conditions.

Figure 1. Evolution of International Symbol of Accessibility (ISA)

Contemporary modifications of ISA, particularly more dynamic and abstract visual solutions, reflect a shift towards a social model of disability, where a person is viewed as an active subject rather than a passive object of assistance. The recognition of the updated symbol in the collection of the Museum of Modern Art in New York confirms its significance for the development of inclusive design and cultural representation of disability. The transition to abstract accessibility symbols can have a number of social effects, including promoting greater inclusion, raising awareness of invisible forms of disability, and reducing stigma. Abstract visual language avoids rigid associations with specific types of impairments and emphasises the diversity of human experience, which is in line with contemporary principles of inclusive and universal design (Чемерис & Барабаш, 2023).

In scientific discourse, it is important to clearly distinguish between the concepts of special, inclusive, accessible and universal design. Special design is aimed at narrow groups of users with specific limitations and involves a high level of personalisation.

Inclusive design focuses on user diversity and social integration, while accessible design aims to remove barriers and meet accessibility standards for people with disabilities and temporary limitations. Universal design, in turn, seeks to create solutions that are suitable for the widest possible audience without the need for additional adaptations. The issue of researching approaches to defining terminology has been presented in previous studies (Chemerys, 2025).

Inclusive and accessible design is seen as an approach to designing software interfaces that ensures equal opportunities for using digital products for the widest possible range of users, regardless of their physical, sensory, cognitive or situational limitations. Research in this area emphasises that accessibility should be incorporated at the early stages of interface development, rather than added after the fact, as this approach is consistent with the principles of universal design and user-centred design. (WCAG, W3C, IAAP).

Scientific studies prove that the problem of software interface accessibility has a clear social and ethical dimension. Inaccessible digital products effectively exclude large groups of users from full participation in educational, professional and communication processes, which contradicts the principles of digital equality and inclusion (Ратушняк et al., 2024). In this context, inclusive design studies are considered not only technical but also interdisciplinary, combining design, computer science, psychology, and social sciences (Льїна, 2025).

The relevance of accessibility research is confirmed by practical results. Empirical studies involving users with disabilities show that interfaces designed with their needs in mind are more understandable, effective, and convenient for all users, not just target groups (Benson-Goldberg, 2025). Thus, accessibility directly correlates with an increase in overall usability, which is confirmed by both academic and applied research in the field of human–computer interaction.

From the point of view of developers and businesses, inclusive design of software interfaces has clearly measurable benefits. Studies show that implementing accessibility standards allows you to expand the audience of a software product, increase user loyalty, and reduce the risks of legal liability associated with non-compliance with digital accessibility legislation (Chemerys, 2022). At the same time, researchers emphasise that systematic accessibility research contributes to the formation of competitive advantages and a positive image for development companies.

Contemporary research pays particular attention to the methodological challenges of inclusive design. These include the insufficient level of training of developers in the field of accessibility, the complexity of integrating WCAG standards into complex software systems, and the need for interdisciplinary collaboration between designers, engineers, and end users (Тїцька, & Ребот, 2024). The latest scientific approaches, in particular the concept of personalised or adaptive interfaces (softerware), emphasise the importance of further research aimed at flexibly configuring interfaces to the individual needs of users (Elavsky et al., 2025).

Thus, research into inclusive and accessible design is critical to the development of modern software interfaces. It forms a scientifically sound basis for creating digital products that meet the requirements of social responsibility, ethical standards and technological efficiency, and are consistent with global trends in digital inclusion and the sustainable development of the information society.

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